

Research Article

Solar-Powered Rainwater Harvesting System: A Proposal for Emergency Water Solutions in Malaysia

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Abstract: In Malaysia, frequently droughts had causes to disruption of municipal water supplies which leaving the communities with the insufficient access of clean and potable water. Previously, Malaysia traditional rainwater harvesting system, designed significantly for non-potable uses failing to meet the need of safe drinking water during emergency. This project critically proposes an innovation of solar-power rainwater harvesting system that inspired from roof harvested rainwater in Australia. The Australian technology with renewable energy integration works to provide potable water during drought and municipal water disruptions. The methodology uses to develop the system includes rooftop catchments, multi-stage filtration, UV sterilization, and solar-powered pumps. The systematic approach of zoning system metering enables smart water distribution with controlled usage. The innovation of system promoting environmental sustainability aligns with Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) principles, ensuring equitable access of clean water for communities, and fostering collaborative governance through partnership with stakeholders. The system encourages sustainable water management, contributing to environmental and impactful solution for water security challenges in Malaysia.

Keywords: Solar-Powered Rainwater Harvesting; Potable Water Management; Emergency Water Distribution.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Malaysia, characterized by its tropical climate is prone to frequently droughts that disrupt municipal water supplies, leaving communities without access to clean and potable water. This issue is further compounded by rapid urbanization and climate change, which intensify the demand for existing water resources (Lani et al., 2018). Rainwater harvesting system (RWH) had been practically used in the world to cope with water supply needs (Campisano et al., 2017). Although RWH have been adopted in some areas in Malaysia, but these are often restricted to non-potable uses such as irrigation, failing to meet the urgent need for safe drinking water during emergencies. Despite with the climate challenges, Malaysia shall utilize the high rainfall distribution with the average 1800-3500 mm in Peninsular Malaysia, 2500-4000 mm in Sarawak while 1500 – 3000 mm in Sabah (MET, n,d). Based on this general rainfall distribution, a study on this proposal particularly constructed to find on the better solution of potable water distribution in Malaysia. Malaysia is blessed with high annual rainfall, hence RWH installation beneficially save the usage of treated water (Shaari, 2020).

This project introduces a solar-powered rainwater harvesting system, aiming to provide potable water during drought or municipal water disruptions. Both critical situations are concern as an emergency which cause daily routine interruptions in residential areas, especially in areas that frequently experience clean water access problems. The system integrates the advanced Australian rainwater harvesting technologies and renewable solar energy for power, ensuring sustainability and reliability (Chubaka et al., 2018). By incorporating smart technologies including zoning system and smart metering or real time monitoring, the project emphasizes fair distribution and promoting sustainable practices. Moreover, the system meets both emergency needs and long -term water management in Malaysia’s residential communities during the critical situations.

The proposed system is aligned with Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) principles making this as a holistic solution for sustainable water development (Radzi et al., 2023). From the aspect of environmental, this system will decrease the dependency on fossil fuel and municipal water supplies which encourage water reservation and mitigate urban flooding challenges. According to Siphambe et al. (2024), flood in a city can be avoided by systematically harvesting, storing rainwater, and using it for multiple purpose. In term of social, it ensures equitable access of potable water such as drinking water, particularly during emergencies, enhancing community resilience. From a governance perspective, this system can be implemented through collaborative partnerships between government agencies, private developers, and local communities in order to meet and supports Malaysia’s climate goals. There is a need for practitioners and policymakers to involve in investments of drinking water systems to support associated economic, security, and public health benefits (Lebu et al., 2024). Integrating ESG principles strengthens the system’s while positioning it as a forward-thinking innovation for sustainable water management.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Rainwater Collection

Rainwater collection start from rooftop catchment areas and channelled through corrosion-resistant gutters into high-capacity storage tanks. The utilization of a first-flush diverter aiming to eliminate the initial runoff containing debris and contaminants, purposely to ensure cleaner water enters the system. To guarantee the durability and safety for potable use, the storage tanks will be constructed from food-grade polyethylene. Overflow mechanisms and level sensors will be a significant integration to ensure the effective water management.

2.2 Filtration and Disinfection

The collected rainwater will flow through a multi-stage filtration system which include the sediment filters as it functions to remove unwanted matters and activated carbon filters to eliminate odors, chemicals, and impurities. Adoption of UV sterilization units works to disinfect the water, ensuring it meets the compliances of potable standards which safe for drinking and cooking. This combination guarantees the safety of water quality for the household usage and avoid any causes of negative impact on communities.

2.3 Solar Power Integration

The system approach is to generate renewable energy for powering pumps, filtration systems, and UV sterilizers through utilization of photovoltaic (PV) panels. Use of lithium-ion battery storage will become as alternative power during nighttime or overcast conditions to avoid operation

interruption. The incorporation of solar energy will decrease the dependency on grid electricity, bolstering the system’s sustainability and resilience during critical situations.

2.4 Zoning for Water Distribution

Each division of residential area will be equipped with flow meter and automated valves to manage water distribution. Strategic zoning system purposely to ensure equitable allocation of water distribution among communities, depends on the population density and demand, while surplus water from one zone can be channelled immediately to another to maximize resource utilization. This approach guarantees fair and efficient distribution of resources in time of crisis.

2.5 Controlled Usage and Automation

The installation of smart meter is needed to monitor household water consumption, enforcing quota-based allocations based on priority uses during emergencies. Sensors will monitor municipal water supply levels and tank capacities, alarming the system automatically during water disruptions happen. To smooth the monitoring from authorize party, a centralized dashboard will provide real-time data on water usage and system performance. Form the centralized dashboard monitoring, it will enable the management efficiency and immediate troubleshooting when needed.

Figure 1. Flowchart depicting the methodology of Solar-Powered Rainwater Harvesting System

Figure 2. Illustration of the proposed Solar-Powered Rainwater Harvesting System

3. FINDINGS

3.1. *Community Perception*

Based on observations, it appears that communities who has trouble during water disruptions, would agree to support the implementation of a potable rainwater harvesting system. From the discussion with communities of a residential area, they highlight a critical need for reliable potable water sources during droughts for their daily usage. Most of the residents acknowledged the long-term benefits of the ability of this advance system which could provide clean water during emergencies, despite some concerns about overall system installation cost. The positive feedback from some of the residents, demonstrate high level of interest and willingness to adopt innovative water solutions.

3.2. *Infrastructure Readiness*

The system centralization which focusing on wide-area rainwater harvesting rather than individual a single unit installation each house. From the assessments of infrastructure, it reveals that public facilities, open spaces, and other centralized locations are suitable for rainwater collection and storage. From another observation, the current distribution network may require modification or extensions to ensure the flow of treated water channelled efficiently from the central system to residential areas. This demonstrates the important of strategic planning to employ the system into existing urban and rural infrastructures.

3.3. *Challenges Identified*

Few challenges have been identified in the effort to implement centralized system. Lack of public awareness among Malaysian especially about the benefits of centralized potable rainwater harvesting remains a major obstacle. Those whom never experience water disruption difficulty will concern on other beneficial project investment instead of spending cost for this system. Additionally, retrofitting or constructing new distribution pipelines to connect the centralized system to homes presents logistical and financial challenges. Another critical challenge is the scarcity of land available

for the installation of rainwater storage tanks, filtration units, and solar arrays, particularly in high populated urban areas. Hence, the importance of stakeholder collaboration and government incentives to facilitate implementation is needed to ensure Malaysia water security well concern. Due to the current increased interest in ESG and sustainability issues brought on by climate change, investors are more interested in developing sustainable investments (Radzi et al., 2023).

4. DISCUSSION

This project proposal of solar-powered rainwater harvesting system offers an innovative solution to Malaysia’s water security issues. By integrating renewable energy and advanced filtration technologies, the system could solve the issue of potable water supply during emergencies. The approach of zoning system addresses the efficiency by distributing water fairly across residential areas, while automation reduces manual intervention and improves operational reliability. Table 1 shows the difference between this proposed system and other rainwater harvesting systems.

Table 1. Comparison of Rainwater Harvesting System

Aspect	Roof Harvested Rainwater in Australia	Rainwater Harvesting in Malaysia	Proposed Solar-Powered Rainwater Harvesting
Purpose	Non-potable uses dominate; potable use in rural areas, some urban households prefer rainwater.	Non-potable uses like gardening and car washing; limited potable application.	Designed for potable water use during emergencies, addressing water security issues.
Collection Method	Rooftop collection with storage tanks in residential and commercial properties.	Rooftop collection with simple storage tanks in individual homes.	Centralized rooftop collection with large, shared storage tanks for multiple households.
Filtration & Treatment	Basic filtration for non-potable use; advanced systems for potable water in rural areas.	Minimal filtration; rarely advanced enough for potable water.	Advanced filtration (sediment, carbon) and UV sterilization for potable water quality.
Distribution	Gravity-fed or pump systems for specific uses within properties.	Simple distribution systems limited to immediate household needs.	Zoning and automated systems for equitable water distribution to multiple households.
Energy Source	Some systems integrate solar pumps but not standardized.	Typically powered by grid electricity; solar use is minimal.	Fully solar-powered with battery storage for uninterrupted operation.
ESG Alignment	Supports environmental sustainability through water conservation.	Limited alignment; mostly focused on water conservation without broader ESG goals.	Strong alignment: promotes sustainability, equitable access, and governance principles.
Scalability	Scalable for urban and rural areas; widespread adoption in urban regions.	Limited to individual households; not widely scalable.	Scalable for urban and rural communities, as well as public and private facilities.

4.1. Challenges

One of the significant challenges faced by the project is the financially due to the high initial installation cost. Advanced technologies such as solar panels, multi-stage filtration systems, and automation mechanisms are costly, which may deter adoption among residents even though they aware the benefit of the system. However, this challenge can be solved if this project receives financial support from government subsidies, partnerships with private developers, and streamlined manufacturing processes for key components. Furthermore, the importance of educating potential users about the long-term cost savings and benefits of the system can help to address concerns about affordability, fostering wider acceptance and implementation.

4.2. Opportunities

Despite these challenges, the positive side of the proposed system presents substantial opportunities. The centralized approach enables for scalability which could make it adaptable for urban residential developments, rural communities, and even public facilities like schools and hospitals. By utilizing Malaysia's abundant rainfall and solar energy, government can look forward on the system that promotes sustainability by reducing reliance on municipal water and fossil fuels. Additionally, it aligns with Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles by ensuring equitable access to clean water during critical situations, fostering community resilience, and encouraging collaborative governance. Furthermore, the system's modular design offers strong commercialization potential, allowing potential developers to invest and collaborate into the new housing projects or retrofit older communities. By addressing Malaysia's water security challenges while supporting environmental goals, the project positions itself as a transformative solution for sustainable water management.

5. CONCLUSION

This project introduces a strong approach to Malaysia's water security problems by embedding solar-powered rainwater harvesting technologies. The system's innovative improved features including advanced filtration, automation, and zoning purposely to ensure the distribution of potable water during emergencies is reliable and equitable. By tackling both critical necessities and long-term sustainability goals, the project has great promise to innovate water management in Malaysia. Partnerships with stakeholders and targeted awareness campaigns will be essential for successful deployment and scalability.

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